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Factors Effecting in Emotional Development of Children of Early Years

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ABSTRACT

Emotional development is related to social development. It refers to feeling of children and expressions about himself and others, and all the situations they faces get control of his body reactions. The child's ability to form satisfying relationships with others and their ability to experience, express, and manage their emotions are all aspects of their emotional development objectives of the study include; finding out the effecting factors in the emotional development of kids, assessing the role of parents in the emotional development of children, to examine the role of teachers in the emotional development of children, to check out the role of peers in the emotional development of kids, how do these factors play their positive role in the emotional development of kids. Through a quantitative approach, a casual comparative research design was used. Data was collected through a random sampling technique from a sample of 60 students, their parents, and teachers, drawn from two schools. Data was collected through questionnaires and observation sheets. Data was analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings reveal the pivotal roles of parents, teachers, caregivers, peers, and cultural influences in shaping children's emotional landscapes. Observations indicate that secure attachments with caregivers foster emotional security and exploration, while peer interactions facilitate emotional expression and social competence. Parental involvement emerges as a significant determinant, with findings highlighting the importance of trust, emotional expression, and supportive communication within parent-child relationships. Based on the findings, recommendations are provided to enhance parental education, implement early childhood interventions, integrate social-emotional learning programs in schools, and foster culturally responsive and trauma-informed practices.

KEYWORDS: Emotional development, Early Grade, Emotions in early years,

INTRODUCTION

Emotional development is a gradual process in which emotional competence develops. In emotional development, a child understands and manages emotions, shows empathy for others, develops a relationship with others, and makes better decisions (Weissberg et al., 2015).

Early emotional development is crucial because it has a lasting effect on people's adult life and interpersonal connections. (Davis & Levine, 2013). The child's ability to form satisfying relationships with others and their ability to experience, express, and manage their emotions are all aspects of their emotional development. (Cohen & others, 2005). The latest research described that the ability of kids to express their own emotions is an important and basic thing for a good relationship with peers (Rubin et al., 2011)

Kids also feel better and can become more confident when making

relationships, and strong bonding is also formed (Domitrovich et al., 2017).

There are eight (Joy, trust, fear, surprise, sadness, disgust, anger, and anticipation) basic feelings. When these basic feelings combine produce other secondary emotions. According to the “Disert Emotion Theory”, there are 34000 thousand emotions but five are core emotions.

i Happiness.

ii Sadness.

iii Anger.

iv Fear.

v Disgust.

Children’s emotional development occur from relationship and connection with people around them. (Environment, Family, Parents, Peers, Teachers). Parents’ emotions affect the emotional development of the children. For example, the mother's responses predict the kid's competence of emotion (Yagmurlu & Altan, 2010). According to research, parents' emotional responses have an impact on their children's emotional growth (Yagmurlu & Altan, 2010). There is a specific relation between parental emotional expression and their children's emotional development. Some studies found that parents affect children's emotional development during their childhood. (Yagmurlu & Altan, 2010;Ahmed et al.,2023). According to Leekam (2004), talking about emotions helps kids comprehend their own and other people's feelings.

Role of Teacher in the Emotional Development of Children

Relationships between teachers and students are linked to early school success, according to research (Hamre & Pianta, 2006). Particularly, how teachers view children's behavior has a big impact on how they interact with their kids (Dobbs & Arnold, 2009).

Relationships between teachers and students have an impact on a child's emotional growth (Murray & Murray, 2004; Howes & Shivers, 2006).

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Several factors contribute to emotional development, including genetic predispositions, family environment, cultural context, social interactions, and educational experiences. Genetic factors play a significant role in emotional development, as certain temperamental traits can be inherited, influencing a child's emotional reactivity and regulation from an early age (Plomin, DeFries, Knopik, & Neiderhiser, 2016).

Different cultures emphasize various emotional expressions and coping mechanisms, which can impact how children learn to manage their emotions (Cole & Tan, 2015). Social interactions, including peer relationships, are crucial in developing emotional skills such as empathy, cooperation, and conflict resolution (Denham, Bassett, & Zinsser, 2012).

High-quality early education programs that incorporate social-emotional learning can significantly enhance children's emotional

development (Jones & Doolittle, 2017).

Tools for Emotional Development

Five dimensions of social-emotional development in children are defined

- (1) Social competence
- (2) Attachment
- (3) Emotional competence
- (4) Self-perceived competence
- (5) temperament/personality

Emotional Development Involves Three Types of Abilities

- I. Emotional recognition,
- ii. Emotional expression and communicational clarity.
- iii. Emotional catharsis (Denham, 2006; Denham, 2007).

The focus of study for many years has been on how day care affects children's cognitive and socio emotional development. Less behavioural issues, improved social skills, and improved academic achievement have all been linked to high-quality care that supports children's emotional skill development (Burchinal et al., 2002; Belsky et al., 2007).

Elements of Emotional Development.

- I. Physical concomitants children
- II. A subjective feeling
- III. Expression of emotion

Stages of Emotional Development

There are three stages of the emotional development of the children.

Dependence

Inter-dependence

Independence

Factors Affecting in Emotional Development of Children

Role of parents in the emotional development of children

Parents as support persons in times of need

Parents as emotional coaches and teachers

Individual differences between parents.

Parenting styles

- I. Authoritative Parenting Style
- II. Authoritarian Parenting Style
- III. Permissive Parenting Style

Attachment with Parents and Emotional Development of Children

The attachment of a child to his mother is the most important factor in the emotional development of a child (Cooper et al., 2009). Parents and caregivers also play a role in the emotional and social development of a child. Lack of attention from parents and caregivers regarding the social and emotional development of a child creates behavioral issues for the child. (Cooper et al., 2009).

Indirect Effects of Parental Characteristics on Emotional Development through Parenting

Parents' behavioral impact on the emotional development of the

children. (Field, 2010 Parental anger is often linked to the use of harsh discipline practices. When parents experience high levels of anger, frustration, or stress, they may be more likely to resort to punitive measures, such as yelling, spanking, or other forms of harsh punishment, as a means of asserting control or reacting to their child's behavior. (Lorber et al., 2016.

The Role of Parent Gender

Several studies were conducted to find out the role of mother and father separately for the emotional development of a child. Because mother and father have different characteristics according to their responsibilities and family structure. Cassano et al. (2007).

Teacher and Student Connection for Emotional Development

The teacher's role is to promote SEL because he is the engine of the class. Many kinds of research revealed that SEL can be taught and measured to promote positive development, reduce problem behavior, and improve students' academic performance, citizenship, and health-related behavior (Zins, 2004).

In the USA, most parents recognize that social and emotional skills are a high priority for their children's success (Princeton Survey Research Associates International, 2015).

How does Friendship Influence Social-Emotional Development?

Friends significantly influence the emotional development of children in several important ways. Additionally, friendships provide opportunities for children to develop empathy; navigating conflicts and offering support allows them to recognize and understand the feelings of others, fostering empathetic responses (Smith et al., 2018).

Peers and Emotional Development

Interacting with peers allows children to practice managing their emotions in social contexts, as they learn to express their feelings appropriately and respond to the emotions of others. This process is crucial for developing emotional competence (Denham et al., 2012). Additionally, peer relationships provide opportunities for children to cultivate empathy; engaging with friends helps them recognize and understand different emotional perspectives, fostering c

Relationship of Emotions with Social Life

1. Some activities can improve the self-recognition of the child like music, dance, crafts, and art. These activities will help in enhancing the motor skills and cognition level of the child.

Compassionate behavior (Smith et al., 2018).

2. Social behavior and real-life situations are taught through the role-play activities in these

Role-play activities are fun for children and these will help them understand real-life situations and social communication skills.

Cultural, Emotional, and Emotional Development

The facial expressions of the children are important to explore the emotional development of the children in their early years. That is why researchers were more interested in observing the facial

expressions of children in their early years. (Ekman, 1973).

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were:

Balance emotional development is important for balancing personality development and success in life. Because the proper emotional development of a child makes sure to succeed in academic and professional life.

1. To find out the factors effecting the emotional development of children
2. To assess the role of parents in the emotional development of children.
3. To examine the role of teachers in the emotional development of children
4. To check out the role of peers in the emotional development of children.
5. To explore the factors that play positive role in the emotional development of children

Research Questions

1. What is the role of parents in the emotional development of kids?
2. What is the role of teachers in the emotional development of kids?
3. How do peers contribute to the emotional development of a child?
4. What are the factors that effect the positive emotional development that contribute a balanced personality in a student?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is descriptive as the researcher used the causal-comparative research method to explore the behavior, characteristics, opinions, attitudes, or behaviors of the population of the study (Creswell, 2012). Causal comparative researches are used to gather numerical, quantitative data, evaluate the data statistically, characterize trends in replies, and test a research topic or hypothesis (Creswell, 2012).

Research Design

The causal comparative research design used to conduct this research study. Causal comparative research design is used to compare current practices, assessments, groups, and program evaluation (Creswell & Clark, 2011).

Population of Study

The population was included all Students of class 1,2 &3 in F.G Junior Public School No.5 (FG JPS No.5), F.G Public School GWA Cantt (FG PS GWA), and F.G Public School Girls GWA Cantt. The total number of each class is 30. Approximately 180 boys and 180 girls were included in this population. Approximately 360 early learners and their parents were the population for this research.

Sample of the Study

A random sampling method was used in this study and 60 students were selected for this purpose. A selection of participants from a population is chosen at random by the researcher using simple

random sampling, a sort of probability sampling. Every person in the population has the same chance of being chosen.

School Name	Boys	Girls
F.G.JPS No.5 GWA	60	60
F.G Public School GWA	60	60
F.G Girls School GWA	60	60
Total	180	180

Research Instruments

In this research, the researcher himself prepared the following instruments for the collection of data:

1. Questionnaire

The questionnaire was prepared on a 5-point Likert scale

2. Questionnaire from Parents

The researcher prepared a questionnaire for the parents of students.

Observation Sheet

The observation sheet was prepared by the researcher to measure the degree of emotional development.

Data Analysis

Collected data was analyzed in SPSS. Descriptive and Inferential Statistics were used for the result.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Parents

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Parental interaction affects the emotional development of the child	Male	47	41.9362	7.97116
	Female	28	39.6429	6.49338
Emotional Intelligence affects the emotional development of the child	Male	47	51.5957	10.55763
	Female	28	49.0714	11.19500
Social Interaction affects the emotional development of the child	Male	47	44.2979	8.01063
	Female	28	39.5714	9.73512

Table 71 shows that the male parents ($M = 41.94$, $SD = 7.97$) and female parents ($M = 39.64$, $SD = 6.49$) exhibit slightly different levels of parental interaction affecting the emotional development of the child. Male parents ($M = 51.59$, $SD = 10.55$) and female parents ($M = 49.07$, $SD = 11.19$) demonstrate varying emotional intelligence levels impacting the child's emotional development. Male parents ($M = 44.29$, $SD = 8.01$) and female parents ($M = 39.5$, $SD = 9.73$) differ in their social interaction's influence on the child's emotional development.

Table 2: *t*-Test Analysis of Parents Regarding Emotional Development of Child

	Male		Female		t(73)	P
	M	SD	M	SD		
Parental interaction affects the emotional development of the child	41.94	7.97	39.64	6.49	1.28	.202
Emotional Intelligence affects the emotional development of the child	51.59	10.55	49.07	11.19	.979	.331
Social Interaction affects the emotional development of the child	44.29	8.01	39.5	9.73	2.279	.026

Table 72 represents the difference in means between male and female parents regarding the impact of parental interaction on emotional development is not statistically significant ($t(73) = 1.28$, $p = .202$). No significant difference exists between male and female parents concerning the influence of emotional intelligence on the child's emotional development ($t(73) = .979$, $p = .331$). Male parents' social interaction significantly affects the child's emotional development compared to female parents ($t(73) = 2.279$, $p = .026$).

Table 3: ANOVA Of Parental Role In The Emotional Development Of The Child

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Parental interaction affects the emotional development of the child	Between Groups		92.283	1	92.283	1.659	.202
	Within Groups	the	4061.237	73	55.633		
	Total	of	4153.520	74			
Emotional Intelligence affects the emotional development of the child	Between Groups		111.810	1	111.810	.959	.331
	Within Groups	the	8511.176	73	116.591		
	Total	of	8622.987	74			
Social Interaction affects the emotional development of the child	Between Groups		391.980	1	391.980	5.193	.026
	Within Groups	the	5510.687	73	75.489		
	Total	of	5902.667	74			

The ANOVA results show that there is no statistically significant difference in emotional development between different parental interaction groups (between groups $F = 1.659$, $p = 0.202$). Overall, parental interaction does not appear to strongly influence

emotional development in this study. Similar to parental interaction, the ANOVA results indicate no significant difference in emotional development related to different levels of emotional intelligence (between groups $F = 0.959$, $p = 0.331$). In contrast, the ANOVA results for social interaction reveal a statistically significant difference (between groups $F = 5.193$, $p = 0.026$). The mean square between groups (391.980) suggests that social interaction has a more pronounced impact on emotional development.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Teachers

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Emotional Intelligence towards the emotional development of the child	Male	23	29.3913	3.47379
	Female	16	31.1250	2.96367
Social Awareness towards the emotional development of the child	Male	23	40.6957	7.06743
	Female	16	42.9375	10.04303
Self-management and Leadership management towards the emotional development of the child	Male	23	44.0000	5.51856
	Female	16	46.1250	6.73177

Table 74 shows that the male teachers ($M = 29.39$, $SD = 3.47$) exhibit slightly lower emotional intelligence scores compared to female teachers ($M = 31.12$, $SD = 2.96$). The smaller standard deviation for both genders suggests less variability in emotional intelligence scores. Male teachers ($M = 40.70$, $SD = 7.07$) and female teachers ($M = 42.94$, $SD = 10.04$) demonstrate varying levels of social awareness impacting children's emotional development. The wider spread of scores among female teachers is reflected in their larger standard deviation. Male teachers ($M = 44.00$, $SD = 5.52$) and female teachers ($M = 46.12$, $SD = 6.73$) differ slightly in their self-management and leadership management skills. Both genders contribute positively to the child's emotional development.

Table 5: t.test Analysis Of Teachers Regarding Emotional Development Of Child

	Male		Female		t(37)	P
	M	SD	M	SD		
Emotional Intelligence towards the emotional development of the child	29.39	3.47	31.12	2.96	-1.625	.113
Social Awareness towards the emotional development of the child	40.69	7.06	42.93	10.04	-.820	.418
Self-management and Leadership management towards the emotional development of the child	44.0	5.51	46.12	6.73	-1.081	.287

development of the child

Table 75 shows the difference in means between male and female teachers is not statistically significant ($t(37) = -1.625, p = .113$). Both genders contribute similarly to emotional intelligence's impact on children. There is no significant difference exists between male and female teachers ($t(37) = -.820, p = .418$). Social awareness affects emotional development similarly across genders. Again, no significant difference is observed ($t(37) = -1.081, p = .287$). Both male and female teachers play comparable roles in self-management and leadership management.

Table 6: ANOVA Of Teachers' Role In The Emotional Development Of The Child

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Emotional Intelligence towards the emotional development of the child	Between Groups	28.361	1	28.361	2.642	.113
	Within Groups	397.228	37	10.736		
	Total	425.590	38			
Social Awareness towards the emotional development of the child	Between Groups	47.424	1	47.424	.672	.418
	Within Groups	2611.807	37	70.589		
	Total	2659.231	38			
Self-management and Leadership management towards the emotional development of the child	Between Groups	42.609	1	42.609	1.168	.287
	Within Groups	1349.750	37	36.480		
	Total	1392.359	38			

The ANOVA results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in emotional development related to different levels of emotional intelligence (between groups $F = 2.642, p = 0.113$). Overall, emotional intelligence does not appear to be a major factor influencing emotional development in this context. Similarly, the ANOVA results for social awareness show no significant difference (between groups $F = 0.672, p = 0.418$). The ANOVA results reveal no significant difference (between groups $F = 1.168, p = 0.287$) related to self-management and leadership management.

DISCUSSION

Factors Affecting Emotional Development of Children in Early Years, widely explores the multifaceted influences shaping emotional development, which is important for social capability, academic achievement, and personal well-being. Emotional development refers to a child's ability to understand, express, and regulate emotions, forming the foundation for building relationships and navigating social situations (Weissberg et al., 2015). The study

identifies various factors, including parental roles, teacher influence, peer relationships, cultural norms, socioeconomic conditions, and technological exposure.

Parents play a critical role in nurturing emotional through secure attachments, effective communication, and caring parenting styles. While opposing factors such as socioeconomic stress, mental health challenges, and marital conflicts negatively impact emotional development (Yagmurlu & Altan, 2010; Hosokawa & Katsura, 2017). Parenting styles also play a significant role like authoritative parenting, which balances nurturance with discipline, and fosters emotional stability and self-esteem, while authoritarian and permissive styles may hinder emotional resilience (Xu et al., 2019).

Teachers also shape emotional understanding through storytelling and structured role-play activities, which promote empathy and emotional expression (Saarni, 1999). Peer relationships are equally influential, providing opportunities for emotional expression, conflict resolution, and the development of empathy. The role of peers in emotional regulation is especially pronounced in early childhood, where cooperative play fosters critical social-emotional skills (Smith et al., 2018).

Cultural and regional contexts also shape emotional development by influencing norms of emotional expression and regulation. (Chen & French, 2020) Additionally, technological exposure has emerged as a modern influence on emotional development. Excessive screen time has been linked to reduced face-to-face interactions, essential for developing empathy and social skills (Madigan et al., 2020). The study employs a causal-comparative research design, data was collected from students, parents, and teachers through questionnaire and observation sheet from Gujranwala cantt schools. It reveals the interconnectedness of these factors in shaping children's emotional development. Overall, this study emphasizes the importance of collaborative efforts by parents, educators, and policymakers to nurture emotionally resilient children capable of thriving in diverse social and academic settings.

CONCLUSION

The emotional development of children is a complex process influenced by several factors. This study has highlighted several key factors that play a significant role in the emotional development of children. Factors of emotional development of children are parents, teachers, caregivers, peers, culture, etc. These factors can better support the emotional development of children. Interventions and programs aimed at promoting positive parenting practices, fostering secure attachments, and enhancing social-emotional learning in schools. By prioritizing the emotional needs of children and creating nurturing environments that foster emotional competence and resilience, we can empower the next generation to thrive emotionally and lead fulfilling lives.

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